

THE IMPACT OF DIFFERENT LEADERSHIP STYLES IN SELECTED ENERGY & UTILITIES ORGANIZATIONS IN KLANG VALLEY: A MODERATING EFFECT OF EMPLOYEE ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS THE SUCCESS OF ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE

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ABSTRACT

The accomplishment of organizational change is greatly influenced by the leadership style employed; however, the success of various approaches may differ based on employee acceptance and perception. Research has been conducted to examine how specific leadership styles influence change initiatives, particularly within the Klang Valley region. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the impact of participatory, laissez-faire, and autocratic leadership styles on the success of organizational change, with employee acceptance as a moderating variable. Quantitative research design was adopted and data were collected through a structured questionnaire using purposive sampling. Responses were obtained from 202 non-managerial employees from selected organizations from the Energy and Utilities industries in Klang Valley. The findings reveal that Laissez-faire Leadership styles exhibit significant relationship with organizational change success; with the strongest positive effect. It was found that Employee Acceptance does not moderate any of these relationships even though in the past literature, Employee Acceptance has significantly moderated the relationships between different styles of leadership and organizational performance. Research has shown that employees' attitude, trust, and commitment significantly impact the relationship between a leadership style and employee performance or engagement. The results offer practical implications for management of organizations in Malaysia to reconsider how generational differences shape work force behaviour toward leaders and organizational performance. For academia, this study contributes new insights into a different perspective on leadership and change management literature. For industry, it supports the development of leadership approaches that minimize resistance and enhance adaptability and workforce performance. For policymakers, the study provides evidence to support leadership training programs that align with millennial generation employee values and national productivity goals. However, this study is limited to non-managerial employees from Klang Valley. Future research should consider expanding the research to include diverse regions, emerging technology related industries, and employee levels.

Keywords: Change Management, Autocratic Leadership, Employee Acceptance, Leadership Styles, Laissez-faire Leadership, Participatory Leadership.

INTRODUCTION

Organizational change is extremely important for every organization. It can be viewed as a process that guides an organization's performance in the direction of achieving its optimal condition. A constantly shifting environment, a response to an ongoing crisis, or a leader's action can all cause organizational transformation. Organizations must adapt to changes nearly constantly in today's business environment if they want to stay competitive (Ameti, 2020). According to Razali et al. (2024), one of the key factors influencing an organization's performance is how it handles change, especially since the environment is volatile and continually evolving, and organizations must compete for the limited resources available. If an organization leadership does not give proper attention to the need for change and the change management process, it may not be able to stay effective.

Beer and Nohria, (2000) in Harvard Business Review revealed that approximately 70 percent of change initiatives in organisations fail. Today's organisations need competent leaders that comprehend the current dynamic and sophisticated business environment (Paais and Pattiruhu (2020). There are various ways to lead, and as such, there are no prescribed universal leadership skills and styles to adopt (Decuypere et al., 2021; Solyom et al., 2023). Additionally, leadership is significantly vital during change as it aid to ensure a successful implementation of change through guidance, support and directing the organisation towards the desired future (Asbari et al., 2021). Jinga et al. (2024) in his studies stressed that by adopting appropriate leadership behaviours such as autocratic, democratic, laissez faire and transactional leaders can create an environment conducive to change, motivate employees, and effectively handle the challenges related with organizational change. This view is supported by work of Zainol et al. (2021) who provided a contemporary review of leadership's role in managing organizational change, identifying effective communication, stakeholder engagement, and resilience as critical factors for success.

With an emphasis on non-managerial staff from Energy and Utilities companies in the Klang Valley, Malaysia, this study attempts to investigate the relationship between participatory, laissez-faire, and authoritarian leadership styles and their effects on organizational change development. The research also investigates the moderating effect of employee engagement on such relationships. The research methodology applied is a quantitative study, and the data collection will be done by distributing questionnaires.

At times of transition, leadership provides the framework, inspiration, and guidance needed to accomplish successful transformation (Asbari et al., 2021). Leaders help develop and communicate the organizational vision and explain the benefits of the change to ensure employee understanding and engagement (Hubbart, 2023). According to Ezimora (2022), leadership offers the framework and guidelines required to overcome resistance and promote the necessary skills and knowledge for change.

Despite the growing body of literature, there remains a notable gap in understanding how different leadership styles can have an impact towards organizational change. Earlier studies are more concerned about reactions to organizational change and how cognitive and behavioural responses have an impact towards organizational change. There are limited studies that dealt with the impact of different leadership styles towards the success of organizational change (Khaw et al., 2022). Effective leadership is at the core of successful organizational transformation (Burke, 2023; Curado & Santos, 2022) and contributes 71% of the success of organizational change (Khaw et al., 2022).

The theory within the context of this study is about the influence of leadership styles on transforming an organization. The theoretical framework identifies three major leadership styles which serve as independent variables, and these include autocratic, laissez-faire, and participatory. These styles are related to the way leaders relate with employees influencing decision making, communication and motivation. Laissez-faire leadership stresses

independence with minimum interference, authoritarian leadership imposes control and organized direction, and participatory leadership encourages participation and teamwork. The moderating variable is introduced as employee acceptance, which reflects the employees' behavioural, emotional, and mental preparedness to embrace change and adopt a certain leadership style. A high degree of employee acceptance can improve performance, motivation, and flexibility, increasing the likelihood that change initiatives will be successful.

The dependent variable in this research is the success of organizational change. How well employees are engaged, motivated, and adaptable during the transition process affects this result. Engaged and contented employees are more inclined to support transformation initiatives and favourably impact the development of their organization. The following research questions are the focus of this study in order to accomplish the research goals:

- RQ1: Is there a significant relationship between participatory leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley?
- RQ2: Is there a significant relationship between laissez-faire leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley?
- RQ3: Is there a significant relationship between autocratic leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley?
- RQ4: Does employee acceptance moderates the relationship between participatory leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley?
- RQ5: Does employee acceptance moderates the relationship between laissez-faire leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley?
- RQ6: Does employee acceptance moderates the relationship between autocratic leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley?

LITERATURE REVIEW

ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE

The process by which a company adjusts its technology, methods, structure, or strategies in response to shifting environmental conditions is known as organizational change (Kumarasinghe & Dilan, 2021). During this condition, it reveals the reaction of the organization to various conditions, among them being globalization, customer expectations, economic advances, and technical breakthroughs (Kharkheli and Gavardashvili, 2022). Ameti (2020) argues that organizational change helps drive a company to the perfect state of performance, especially the present competitive environment.

Workforce diversity and globalization, as well as customer preferences are major internal factors and influence. external change agents. Indicatively, workforce diversity encourages creativity through the introduction of. diverse perspectives, as through globalization it is possible to unify business activities across. national borders (Ju & Kim, 2025). Change in consumer expectation is also very rapid hence compelling companies. to adapt and stay current. Technological innovations impact significantly on the way organizations. perform. The way that teams engage and how they work has been transformed by the advancement of information technology. making future work, remote work, and digital collaborations common (Momani, 2024).

On the same note, there are social, political, and legal issues that still affect the strategic choices made by organizations. Organizational transformation when done correctly enhances productivity, morale, flexibility, etc. innovation, and ultimately profitability (Abbas, 2022). Nevertheless, change process is poorly managed. may result in employee resisting and failure, thus it is essential to identify the importance of the role of. leadership and acceptance of employees as the way of changing successfully.

LEADERSHIP STYLES AND ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE

Three leadership styles are covered in this study: Participatory, Laissez-Faire, and Autocratic.

Participatory Leadership Style and Organizational Change

As part of the participatory leadership, leaders and their team members collaborate and take decisions jointly. This is the best style of leadership in terms of enhancing innovation, trust, and morale. At environments with a high emphasis on creativity and solutions (Khasawneh and Elrehail, 2022). According to Khasawneh & Elrehail, (2022) participatory leadership increases desire to change. projects and enhances job satisfaction thus, making organizational more flexible. The following hypothesis is put forth in this study:

H1: There is a significant relationship between participatory leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley.

Laissez-Faire Leadership Style and Organizational Change

Workers with laissez-faire leadership can make decisions with a minimum of interference on their manager's part. This leadership style is appropriate since employees possess the right to their professional life and can be highly stimulating to the process of change management (Northouse, 2021). This may lead to innovation among very talented teams but failure to do so can resort to poor leadership, ambiguous roles and lack of coordination (Desgourdes et al., 2023). According to studies, this style may lead to stress and loss of trust, both of which are negative to organizational change initiatives (Muktamar and Nurnaningsih, 2024; Lundmark et al., 2022). Therefore, the following hypothesis is put forth:

H2: There is a significant relationship between laissez-faire leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley.

Autocratic Leadership Style and Organizational Change

Autocratic leadership is characterized by stringent control and centralized decision-making. Although it functions well in organization where compliance or high pressure are common, it can be an obstacle, demoralizing and undermining creativity (Husnain, 2023). Research has shown that in cases of autocratic leadership, when it is fully applied in a strict manner, it may lead to the resistance, reduced creativity and performance in organization transformation situations (Asno et al., 2023; Husnain, 2023). Consequently, the following hypothesis is put forth:

H3: There is a significant relationship between autocratic leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley.

It is the willingness and readiness of employees to participate in a specific project, and is referred to as employee acceptance (Syarif et al., 2024). New procedures, technology or new styles of leadership that are implemented are adopted by employees during change projects. It indicates how employees respond to change in the organization at the psychological, behavioural, emotional, and behavioural level. Employee positive perceptions of change promote higher chance that they will stand by the process and contribute in making it a success. Employees who oppose the change or become alienated to it, in its turn, are more likely to hamper its implementation and create conflicts. According to Rialti and Fileri (2024), the employees should be informed about any changes, which must be updated regularly. The employees would be more likely to accept leaders who address issues, are open, and communicate, and provide unremitting advice. When employees feel valued and supported, they are more likely to commit to the changes introduced by leadership. The study of moderating role of employee engagement in the relationship between diverse leadership styles and performance of organization remains under-examined in Malaysian context towards the millennial era. In studies conducted by Chukwuma and Zondo (2024) it emphasizes that employee acceptance moderates the relationship between leadership style and change outcomes. Participatory leadership may be more successful in organizations where employees are open to contributing ideas and engaging in team-based decision-making. If employee acceptance is low, even participatory leadership may fail to bring desired results. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H4: There is a significant moderating effect of employee acceptance towards the relationship between participatory leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley.

In a laissez-faire environment, employee acceptance plays a critical role in determining how effectively change is adopted. Laissez-faire leadership provides freedom and autonomy, but its effectiveness is contingent on whether employees are self-motivated and willing to adapt to responsibilities independently. Without employee acceptance, this leadership style may lead to confusion and a lack of direction. Eisenhardt and Martin (2021) conducted research on technology firms in the United States, and discovered that while certain extent of autonomy enhances innovation, lack of leader presence causes strategic misalignment and ineffective decisions. Mugenda & Were's (2022) survey on corporate firms in South Africa revealed that passive leadership resulted to demotivated workers, less creativity, and unsatisfactory implementation of strategies and Ngugi and Were (2021) conducted research on the Kenyan manufacturing firms discovered that organizations operating under the system experienced poor efficiency, accountability, and engagement. Hence, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H5: There is a significant moderating effect of employee acceptance towards the relationship between laissez-faire style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley.

In the case of autocratic leadership, employee acceptance influences how directives and changes are received by subordinates. Autocratic leaders make fast, top-down decisions, which may be efficient in crises or highly structured environments. However, without employee acceptance, this leadership style can lead to dissatisfaction, decreased morale, and resistance. The influence of authoritarian leadership on employee performance has been studied. Gultom (2022) claims that authoritarian leadership has a big impact on employee

performance, however research carried out by (Caillier, 2020) states that there is a considerable negative association between views of authoritarian leadership style and employee performance. Thus, the following hypothesis is presented:

H6: There is a significant moderating effect of employee acceptance towards the relationship between autocratic leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley.

Figure 1 depicts the Theoretical Framework based on the past literature and conceptual framework.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a structured questionnaire via Google Form to gather responses from the target population. The study aimed to examine whether there is a significant relationship between leadership styles and employee acceptance, with organizational change as the key contextual variable. It focused on understanding how different leadership styles; participatory, laissez-faire, and autocratic leadership styles that influence employee acceptance of change, with a quantitative approach used for analysis. The target population in this research includes non-managerial employees working in selected Energy and Utilities organizations in Klang Valley, Malaysia, that are currently undergoing or have recently undergone organizational change. These individuals were selected because they are directly impacted by leadership decisions and are often at the receiving end of change initiatives.

Using purposive sampling, a pilot study with thirty respondents was first carried out. The purpose of this pilot was to make sure the questionnaire was clear and reliable and to identify any possible problems before it was fully implemented. Several statements' wording was slightly rephrased in response to feedback in order to make them easier for respondent to comprehend. In order to ensure complete responses and prevent data loss, every question was also made mandatory. In order to serve the working population, which usually operates in English-speaking workplaces, the survey was distributed in English.

After the pilot study, 202 respondents were targeted for the full-scale survey, which was distributed over a 10-day period. The sample size was calculated using G*Power software (effect size = 0.2, α = 0.05, power = 0.8), with a 5% buffer included to account for potential attrition. Using a priori power analysis and the G*Power 3.1 software (Erdfelder et al., 2009), a commonly used method in social science research (Giebelhausen et al., 2021; Memon et al., 2020), the minimal sample size needed for this study was established. Based on the inputs mentioned above, the G*Power analysis showed that in order to reliably detect the

hypothesized effects, a minimum of 191 respondents is needed. The overall sample size was 201 after the sampling size was raised by 5% to meet the study's goals and produce statistically significant results. The initial sample size was modified based on the anticipated attrition rate, such as the percentage of dropouts or non-responses, in order to ensure that a sufficient number of respondents complete the survey (Ahmed, 2024). To ensure sufficient representative and varied sample, respondents were chosen using purposive sampling from Energy and Utilities companies in the region of Klang Valley. Only fully completed questionnaires were included in the data analysis.

INSTRUMENT DEVELOPMENT

The primary instrument for this study was a structured, self-administered questionnaire distributed via Google Form. All items were made mandatory in order to ensure the consistency and completeness of the data. All of the questions on the questionnaire were closed-ended, thus being appropriate for statistical analysis. There were four sections to the instrument. Items to gather demographic information, including gender, race, age, educational background, and length of employment, were included in Section A. Section B has fifteen items covering the three sub-dimensions of participatory, laissez-faire, and authoritarian leadership in relation to perceptions of leadership styles. Five measures evaluating trust, motivation, satisfaction, and readiness to follow leadership throughout change were utilized in Section C, which was allocated to employee acceptance. Five items on how leadership influenced understanding and adaptability toward change initiatives were included in Section D, which investigated on organizational change. A 5-point Likert scale was used to rate each item in Sections B, C, and D (1 being strongly disagree and 5 being strongly agree). The instruments created by Fatoki et al. (2023), Desgourdes et al. (2023), and Du et al. (2020) were modified from previously validated instruments. Additionally, a respondent-driven pretest was used in this study to assess the instrument's ease of use, contextual fit, and practical clarity. Ten respondents who met the specified inclusion criteria were chosen. Minor modifications were made in response to the respondents' comments. To improve interpretability across various demographic groups, a number of sentences were also made simpler. The questionnaire took an average of eight to twelve minutes to complete, which is consistent with best practices in survey design to reduce tiredness and sustain participation (Bougie & Sekaran, 2020).

RESULTS

The investigation specifically focuses on how different styles of leadership affect organizational transformation. Furthermore, the role that employee acceptance plays in influencing the relationship between different styles of leadership and the success of organizational transformation has been investigated.

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

Data from 202 valid and completed responses gathered from different Klang Valley organizations were analysed for this study. According to a demographic analysis, 33.2% of respondents were women and 66.8% of respondents were men. In terms of ethnicity, 48.5% were Malay, 37.1% Indian, 12.4% Chinese, and 2% from other ethnic backgrounds. Most respondents (60.4%) were aged between 20 to 30 years. The majority held a degree (65.3%), while others had diplomas (14.9%), master's degrees (9.9%), or SPM qualifications (9.9%). Regarding work experience, 34.2% had 5–10 years of tenure, followed by 29.7% with 3–5 years, 23.3% with 1–2 years, and 12.9% with over 10 years of experience. A brief demographic analysis of the 202 respondents was performed on the data from Section A of the questionnaires. A summary of demographic data is illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents: n= [202]

Variables		n= [202]	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	135	66.8%
	Female	67	33.2%
Age	20 years – 30 years	122	60.4%
	31 years – 40 years	71	35.1%
	41 years – 50 years	9	4.5%
	51 years and above	0	0%
Education	Secondary School (SPM)	20	9.9%
	Diploma	30	14.9%
	Bachelor's Degree	132	65.3%
	Master's Degree	20	9.9%
Working Tenure	1 – 2 years	47	23.3%
	3 – 5 years	60	29.7%
	5 – 10 years	69	34.2%
	10 years and above	26	12.9%
Race	Malay	98	48.5%
	Chinese	25	12.4%
	Indian	75	37.1%
	Other	4	2.0%

ANALYSIS OF MEASURES

Analysis of measure were carried out to show a detailed analysis on all five main variables that is included in the questionnaire. Tables 2 to 6 below display the frequency distribution and percentage of responses of each item. This analysis will guide in understanding the prevailing opinions and tendencies of the respondents to different leadership style, level of employee favourable recognition and organizational change success rate.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Responses for Participatory Leadership Style Items

Code Item	Strongly Disagree (F, %)	Disagree (F, %)	Neutral (F, %)	Agree (F, %)	Strongly Agree (F, %)
PLS1 My manager involves me in decision-making processes and considers my input	9 (4.5%)	47 (23.3%)	55 (27.2%)	64 (31.7%)	27 (13.4%)
PLS2 I am encouraged by my manager to share my ideas and suggestions during team discussions	5 (2.5%)	28 (13.9%)	39 (19.3%)	83 (41.1%)	47 (23.3%)
PLS3 My manager fosters an environment of collaboration where my opinion matters	8 (4.0%)	30 (14.9%)	59 (29.2%)	70 (34.7%)	35 (17.3%)
PLS4 My manager regularly consults with me to solve problems together	14 (6.9%)	37 (18.3%)	48 (23.8%)	70 (34.7%)	33 (16.3%)
PLS5 My manager values my feedback and incorporates it into work-related decisions	9 (4.5%)	31 (15.3%)	46 (22.8%)	73 (36.1%)	43 (21.3%)

For the Participatory Leadership Style items, the frequency distribution of the responses is presented in Table 2. For the item "My manager involves me in decision-making processes and considers my input" (PLS1), agreed and strongly agreed 45.1%, and disagreed and strongly disagreed 27.8%. The remaining 27.2% were neutral. The highest level of agreement was for PLS2, with 64.4% of respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing that they are encouraged to share ideas with team members during team discussions. The last group, PLS4 (51.0%), was the one exhibiting the lowest agreement and referred to managers involving employees to solve problems together. In general, respondents displayed moderate to positive perceptions regarding the participatory leadership practices in their organizations.

Overall, the responses indicate that participatory leadership is perceived moderately to positively, with varying levels of agreement across different aspects. The highest frequency of strong agreement was observed in PLS2, highlighting that employees feel most encouraged to share ideas during discussions. Conversely, PLS4 had the lowest frequency of strong agreement, suggesting that employees may feel less involved in collaborative problem-solving. Additionally, PLS1 exhibited a notable proportion of disagreement (27.8%), indicating a divided perception regarding managerial involvement in decision-making. These variations suggest that while participatory leadership is present, its effectiveness in different areas may be inconsistent.

Table 3 . Frequency Distribution of Responses for Laissez-faire Leadership Style Items

Code Item	Strongly Disagree		Neutral	Strongly Agree	
	(F, %)	(F, %)		(F, %)	(F, %)
LLS1 My manager allows me to work independently without providing constant direction	7 (3.5%)	32 (15.8%)	53 (26.2%)	75 (37.1%)	35 (17.3%)
LLS2 I am trusted by my manager to make decisions about my tasks and responsibilities	4 (2.0%)	27 (13.4%)	46 (22.8%)	76 (37.6%)	49 (24.3%)
LLS3 My manager rarely intervenes unless I specifically ask for assistance or clarification	10 (5.0%)	22 (10.9%)	53 (26.2%)	61 (30.2%)	56 (27.7%)
LLS4 My manager gives me the freedom to approach my work in the way I find most effective	10 (5.0%)	28 (13.9%)	37 (18.3%)	76 (37.6%)	51 (25.2%)
LLS5 I receive minimal supervision and am encouraged to take ownership of my projects	11 (5.4%)	28 (13.9%)	40 (19.8%)	72 (35.6%)	51 (25.2%)

Table 3 displays the frequency distribution for Laissez-faire Leadership Style items. More than 50 % agreed or strongly agreed with most items in this category. In this case, for example, 61.9% agreed or strongly agreed that they are trusted to make decisions about their tasks (LLS2), and 62.8% agreed or strongly agreed that they have freedom to approach work effectively (LLS4). Agreement was the strongest (60.8%) regarding minimal supervision and ownership encouragement (LLS5).

Overall, the findings suggest that laissez-faire leadership is well-practiced in the organizations surveyed, with a general agreement exceeding 50% across most items. The highest frequency of strong agreement was observed for LLS4 (62.8%), indicating that employees highly value the freedom to approach their work in a way they find most effective. On the other hand, while LLS5 (60.8%) also showed strong agreement regarding minimal supervision, it had the lowest frequency of strong agreement among the three highest-rated items, suggesting that while employees appreciate autonomy, there may still be a need for some level of managerial oversight. These results reinforce the presence of laissez-faire leadership as a significant management style in Klang Valley organizations.

Table 4. Frequency Distribution of Responses for Autocratic Leadership Style Item

Code Item	Strongly Disagree		Neutral	Strongly Agree	
	(F, %)	(F, %)		(F, %)	(F, %)
ALS1 My manager makes decisions without consulting me and considering my input	29 (14.4%)	47 (23.3%)	54 (26.7%)	52 (25.7%)	20 (9.9%)
ALS2 My manager closely monitors my work and provides strict instructions on how tasks should be completed	24 (11.9%)	58 (28.7%)	45 (22.3%)	51 (25.2%)	24 (11.9%)
ALS3 I am expected to follow my manager's orders without questioning their authority	38 (18.8%)	41 (20.3%)	47 (23.3%)	38 (18.8%)	38 (18.8%)
ALS4 My manager discourages independent thinking from me and	41 (20.3%)	58 (28.7%)	35 (17.3%)	41 (20.3%)	27 (13.4%)

	expects tasks to be done exactly as directed					
ALS5	My manager maintains strict control over my processes and outcomes	32 (15.8%)	54 (26.7%)	45 (22.3%)	33 (16.3%)	38 (18.8%)

Table 4 shows the frequency distribution for Autocratic Leadership Style items. On item "My manager makes decisions without consulting me" (ALS1), 37.7% disagreed/strongly disagreed, and 35.6% agreed/strongly agreed. Accordingly, 39.1 % disagreed that they are supposed to adhere to orders without questioning the authority's command (ALS3). The most strongly disagreed statement reached an agreement of 49.0% for ALS4, which expressed discouragement of independent thinking. This shows that the use and acceptability of autocratic leadership practices are less in the surveyed organizations.

Overall, the findings indicate a lower acceptance of autocratic leadership practices within the surveyed organizations. The highest frequency of strong disagreement was observed for ALS4 (49.0%), suggesting that discouragement of independent thinking is the most prominent aspect of autocratic leadership experienced by employees. Conversely, ALS3 recorded the highest disagreement (39.1%), implying that a significant portion of employees reject the idea of unquestioning adherence to authority. The divided responses for ALS1 further highlight the mixed perceptions of decision-making autonomy, where a comparable proportion of employees both agreed and disagreed. These variations suggest that while autocratic leadership exists, it is not the dominant or most accepted leadership style in the surveyed organizations.

Table 5. Frequency Distribution of Responses for Employee Acceptance Items

Code Item	Strongly Disagree (F, %)	Disagree (F, %)	Neutral (F, %)	Agree (F, %)	Strongly Agree (F, %)
EA1 I feel confident following my manager's decisions, even when I disagree	12 (5.9%)	30 (14.9%)	57 (28.2%)	80 (39.6%)	23 (11.4%)
EA2 I trust that my manager's leadership style is aimed at benefiting me as an employee	10 (5.0%)	31 (15.3%)	47 (23.3%)	76 (37.6%)	38 (18.8%)
EA3 I am more willing to accept change when it is introduced by my manager	14 (6.9%)	23 (11.4%)	56 (27.7%)	74 (36.6%)	35 (17.3%)
EA4 I trust that my manager's leadership style is aimed at benefiting me as an employee	14 (6.9%)	25 (12.4%)	48 (23.8%)	73 (36.1%)	42 (20.8%)
EA5 I find it easy to adapt to my manager's way of leading the team	15 (7.4%)	31 (15.3%)	46 (22.8%)	61 (30.2%)	49 (24.3%)

Frequency of distribution for Employee Acceptance items is presented in Table 5. In the case of item "I feel confident following my manager's decisions, even when I disagree" (EA1), 51.0% agreed or strongly agreed, and 20.8% disagreed. The item EA4, "The manager and his or her style of leadership is to be trusted as from the employees' standpoint this leadership is beneficial to the employees," received the highest (56.9%) agreement. The item with the highest positive response (54.5%) was the ease of adapting to the manager's leadership style (EA5). The results of these findings indicate some degree of positive acceptance of employees towards the leadership style of their managers.

Overall, the findings suggest a generally positive acceptance of leadership styles among employees. The highest frequency of strong agreement was recorded for EA4 (56.9%), indicating that employees perceive their managers' leadership as trustworthy and beneficial. Similarly, EA5 (54.5%) showed strong positive responses, suggesting that employees find it relatively easy to adapt to their managers' leadership styles. Meanwhile, EA1, with 51.0% agreement, reflects employees' confidence in following managerial decisions, even when they personally disagree. The lower disagreement rate (20.8%) in EA1 further reinforces the trend of positive acceptance. These results highlight that while acceptance levels vary, employees generally have a favourable view of their managers' leadership approaches.

Table 6. Frequency Distribution of Responses for Organizational Change Success Items

Code Item	Strongly Disagree (F, %)	Disagree (F, %)	Neutral (F, %)	Agree (F, %)	Strongly Agree (F, %)
OCS1 I understand the importance of the organizational change and how it impacts my company	2 (1.0%)	9 (4.5%)	40 (19.8%)	100 (49.5%)	51 (25.2%)
OCS2 I believe that the organizational change is necessary for the long-term growth of the organization	1 (0.5%)	9 (4.5%)	44 (21.8%)	88 (43.6%)	60 (29.7%)
OCS3 I believe in top management leadership direction and initiatives, which motivate me to support and achieve the goals of organizational change	3 (1.5%)	15 (7.4%)	45 (22.3%)	89 (44.1%)	50 (24.8%)
OCS4 I am more likely to support and implement organizational changes when my manager provides clear and consistent guidance	0 (0.0%)	12 (5.9%)	45 (22.3%)	79 (39.1%)	66 (32.7%)
OCS5 When my manager addresses my concerns about change, I feel more confident in contributing to the success of organizational change	4 (2.0%)	14 (6.9%)	35 (17.3%)	80 (39.6%)	69 (34.2%)

Table 6 displays the frequency distribution for Organizational Change Success items. Of all these variables, this received the most positive responses. For instance, 74.7% of the respondents strongly believe or agree with OCS1 (Understand the importance of organizational change), and 73.3% believe that organizational change is needed for long-term growth (OCS2). The item with the highest agreement was OCS5 (73.8%) from the set about feeling confident in contributing to change when managers address concerns. These items tend to be disagreed upon by very few respondents, suggesting overall wide support for organizational change initiatives.

Overall, the findings indicate strong support for organizational change among employees. The highest frequency of strong agreement was observed for OCS5 (73.8%), highlighting the importance of managers addressing employee concerns to encourage active participation in change efforts. Similarly, OCS1 (74.7%) and OCS2 (73.3%) reflect employees' recognition of the necessity and long-term benefits of change. The consistently low disagreement rates (below 10%) further reinforce the widespread acceptance of organizational transformation. These results suggest that employees generally view change initiatives positively, especially when they feel involved and reassured by leadership.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Table 7. Correlation Analysis Results

		Participatory Leadership Style	Laissez- faire Leadership Style	Autocratic Leadership Style	Organizational Change Success
Participatory Leadership Style	Pearson	1	.649**	-.537**	.446**
	Correlation				
	Sig. (2- tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	202	202	202	202
Laissez-faire Leadership Style	Pearson	.649**	1	-.556**	.559**
	Correlation				
	Sig. (2- tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001
	N	202	202	202	202
Autocratic Leadership Style	Pearson	-.537**	-.556**	1	-.401**
	Correlation				
	Sig. (2- tailed)	<.001	<.001		<.001
	N	202	202	202	202
Organizational Change Success	Pearson	.446**	.559**	-.401**	1
	Correlation				
	Sig. (2- tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	202	202	202	202

Based on Table 7 above using Ratnasari et al., (2016) on the interpretation of r in Pearson Correlation; the results of data analysis revealed a correlation between Participatory Leadership Style and Organizational Change Success is moderately positive ($r = 0.446$, $p < 0.001$). Therefore, higher levels of participatory leadership in leading an organization to implement successful change initiatives are suggested.

There is a clear and stronger positive correlation between Laissez-faire Leadership Style and Organizational Change Success ($r = 0.559$, $p < 0.001$). This indication of moderately strong relationship between the variables, implies that leadership approaches involving provision of autonomy and independence to employees may be particularly effective in promoting organizational change.

A moderate negative correlation exists between Autocratic Leadership Style and Organizational Change Success ($r = -0.401$, $p < 0.001$). This negative relationship means that organizations around Klang Valley could benefit from better implementation of organizational change if the leadership took a less autocratic approach.

It is interesting to note that intercorrelations of leadership styles also emerge from the analysis. Laissez-faire and Participatory styles are positively correlated ($r = 0.649$, $p < 0.001$) and both have high but negative correlations with autocratic leadership style ($r = -0.537$ and $r = -0.556$ respectively, $p < 0.001$). These indicate that certain leadership styles co-exist in organizations.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Table 8. Regression Coefficients of each style of leadership

Coefficients ^a		Unstandardized		Standardized		Sig.
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	2.677	.312		8.581	<.001
	Participatory Leadership Style	.083	.059	.113	1.419	.158
	Laissez-faire Leadership Style	.321	.060	.429	5.310	<.001
	Autocratic Leadership Style	-.063	.045	-.103	-1.410	.160

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Change Success

The regression coefficients of each style of leadership are illustrated in Table 8 above. The regression equation can be stated as follows: Organizational Change Success = 2.677 + 0.083(Participatory) + 0.321(Laissez-faire) - 0.063(Autocratic). Out of the three leadership styles, Laissez Faire Leadership is found to be a major predictor of successful organizational change in this multi variate context.

MODERATION ANALYSIS

Table 9. Moderation Analysis for the Effect of Employee Acceptance on the Relationship Between Leadership Styles and Organizational Change Success.

Leadership Style	B	SE	t	Sig.
Participatory Leadership Style				
PPLS(X)	0.02	0.06	0.31	
Employee Acceptance (EA)	0.45***	0.06	7.29	> 0.05
PPLS × EA	0.05	0.03	1.62	
F	40.24***			
R ²	0.37***			
Laissez-Faire Leadership Style				
LLS (X)	0.22***	0.06	3.63	
Employee Acceptance (EA)	0.32***	0.06	5.44	> 0.05
LLS × EA	0.05	0.03	1.47	
F	48.88***			
R ²	0.41***			
Autocratic Leadership Style				
ALS (X)	-0.10**	0.04	-2.75	

Employee Acceptance (EA)	0.36***	0.05	7.79 >0.05
ALS × EA	0.03	0.03	0.91
F	41.27***		
R²	0.38***		

Note. N = 202. *p < .05; **p < .01; ***p < .001.

Based on Table 9 on moderation analysis, the result of Hypothesis 4 (H4) is not statistically significant as the interaction between Participatory Leadership Style and Employee Acceptance (PLS × EA) is not significant (B = 0.05, t = 1.62, p > 0.05). Therefore, H4 is not supported, indicating that employee acceptance does not substantially moderate the association between participatory leadership and organizational change success. It is noted that although the direct effect of participatory leadership (B = 0.02, t = 0.31, p > 0.05) is not significant with organizational change success, employee acceptance (B = 0.45, t = 7.29, p < 0.001) itself has a strong positive direct effect with organizational change success.

Meanwhile, the result of Hypothesis 5 (H5) shows that the interaction between Laissez-faire Leadership Style and Employee Acceptance (LLS × EA) is also not statistically significant (B = 0.05, t = 1.47, p > 0.05). Therefore, H5 is not supported. Nevertheless, Laissez-faire leadership (B = 0.22, t = 3.63, p < 0.001) and employee acceptance (B = 0.32, t = 5.44, p < 0.001) have a significant direct relationship with organizational change success. In the conditional effects analysis, the interaction between the policies and legal environment with Laissez-faire leadership does not have net significance, but the results do suggest that Laissez-faire leadership has stronger effects at higher employee acceptance.

As for Hypothesis 6 (H6), the interaction between Autocratic Leadership Style and Employee Acceptance (ALS × EA) is not significant (B = 0.03, t = 0.91, p > 0.05). Therefore, H6 is not supported. Using Autocratic leadership as the independent variable, there was a significant negative direct effect (B = -0.10, t = -2.75, p < 0.01) with organizational change success and Employee Acceptance have a significant positive effect (B = 0.36, t = 7.79, p < 0.001) with organizational change success. Autocratic leadership's conditional effects show that the effect is a stronger negative one when the level of employee acceptance is lower.

Although nothing may be said statistically about all three moderation hypotheses (H4, H5, H6), the analysis finds several important direct effects. As shown by both standard and empirical values of R² (being range 0.37–arc 0.41 and p < 0.001), all three models demonstrate highly significant values, showing that leadership style and staff acceptance for organizational change, overall explain a significant portion of variance in success of organizational change. Employee acceptance is a consistent significant positive predictor across all models, meaning it is important in all leadership styles.

Table 10. Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Description	Statistical Evidence	Result	Interpretation
H1	There is a significant relationship between participatory leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley.	$\beta = 0.113, t = 1.419, p = 0.158$	Not Supported	Participatory leadership style does not have a statistically significant direct effect on organizational change success.
H2	There is a significant relationship between laissez-faire leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley.	$\beta = 0.429, t = 5.310, p < 0.001$	Supported	Laissez-faire leadership style has a significant positive effect on organizational change success. This suggests that giving employees autonomy and independence is beneficial for change implementation.
H3	There is a significant relationship between autocratic leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley.	$\beta = -0.103, t = -1.410, p = 0.160$	Not Supported	Autocratic leadership style does not have a statistically significant direct effect on organizational change success.
H4	There is a significant moderating effect of employee acceptance on the relationship between participatory leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley.	Interaction term (PLS \times EA): $B = 0.05, t = 1.62, p > 0.05$	Not Supported	Employee acceptance does not significantly moderate the relationship between participatory leadership style and organizational change success.
H5	There is a significant moderating effect of employee acceptance on the relationship between laissez-faire leadership style and the success of organizational change in Klang Valley.	Interaction term (LLS \times EA): $B = 0.05, t = 1.47, p > 0.05$	Not Supported	Employee acceptance does not significantly moderate the relationship between laissez-faire leadership style and organizational change success.
H6	There is a significant moderating effect of employee acceptance on the relationship between autocratic leadership style and	Interaction term (ALS \times EA): $B = 0.03, t = 0.91, p > 0.05$	Not Supported	Employee acceptance does not significantly moderate the relationship between autocratic leadership style and

leadership style and the
success of organizational
change in Klang Valley.

organizational change
success.

The first hypothesis (H1) stated that there is a significant relationship between the participatory leadership style and organizational change success. There is no support to this hypothesis as per the multiple regression analysis results ($\beta = 0.113$, $t = 1.419$, $p = 0.158$). Thus, hypothesis 1 is not supported. The correlation analysis on the relationship between participatory leadership and organizational change success revealed positive correlation, although this relationship was not significant in the regression model where other leadership styles were controlled for. It follows that the success of organizational change because of participatory leadership cannot be achieved by itself without involvement of other leadership approaches.

The second hypothesis (H2) stated that there is a significant relationship between the laissez-faire leadership style and organizational change success. The regression results show that ($\beta = 0.429$, $t = 5.310$, $p < 0.001$), thus hypothesis 2 is strongly supported. It was found that laissez-faire leadership was the strongest predictor of organizational change success among the three leadership styles. The findings suggest that autonomy, independence, and minimal supervision may be the most appropriate approach when implementing successful organizational change among Klang Valley organizations.

The third hypothesis (H3) stated that there is a significant relationship between the autocratic leadership style and organizational change success. There is no support to this hypothesis as per the multiple regression analysis results ($\beta = -0.103$, $t = -1.410$, $p = 0.160$). Thus, hypothesis 3 is not supported. The findings suggest that organizations in Klang Valley should take a less autocratic approach when dealing with organizational change. Although autocratic leadership has a negative correlation with organizational change success, its individual impact does not have strong enough effect to achieve statistical significance in the multivariate model.

The fourth hypothesis (H4) stated that employee acceptance moderates the relationship between participatory leadership and the success of the organizational change. There is no support to this hypothesis as per the moderation analysis results ($B = 0.05$, $t = 1.62$, $p > 0.05$). Thus, hypothesis 4 is not supported. Although participatory leadership and employee acceptance has a direct effect, it was found that Employee acceptance does not moderate to the relationship between participatory leadership and organizational change success.

The fifth hypothesis (H5) stated that employee acceptance moderates the relationship between laissez-faire leadership and the success of the organizational change. There is no support to this hypothesis as per the moderation analysis results ($B = 0.05$, $t = 1.47$, $p > 0.05$). Thus, hypothesis 5 is not supported. Although laissez-faire leadership and employee acceptance has a direct effect, it was found that Employee acceptance does not moderate to the relationship between laissez-faire leadership and organizational change success.

The sixth hypothesis (H6) stated that employee acceptance moderates the relationship between autocratic leadership and the success of the organizational change. There is no support to this hypothesis as per the moderation analysis results ($B = 0.03$, $t = 0.91$, $p > 0.05$). Thus, hypothesis 6 is not supported. Although autocratic leadership and employee acceptance has a direct effect, it was found that Employee acceptance does not moderate to the relationship between autocratic leadership and organizational change success.

DISCUSSION

For managers and organizational leaders seeking to improve employee engagement and promote long-term organizational success through effective leadership strategies, this study offers insightful information.

The results of this study highlight how important leadership styles are in developing employee engagement, which is a major driver for organizational success. Among the leadership styles examined, it was found that laissez-faire leadership has a significant relationship and pose the strongest predictor (H2) of organizational change success among the three leadership styles. The findings suggest that autonomy, independence, and minimal supervision may be the most appropriate approach when implementing successful organizational change among non-managerial employees from Energy and Utilities organizations in Klang Valley in the present day. Laissez-faire leadership emerged as the most influential, highlighting the effectiveness of leaders who prioritize employee's empowerment and personal development. This reinforces the view that modern organizational contexts benefit greatly from leadership that put trust in their people. This could also be the key traits and values of the new generational workforce that wants flexibility and autonomy e.g. strong preference for hybrid models, self-directed work, and control over how and when they work; appreciate well-being & mental health e.g. high priority on mental health support, stress reduction, and the need for work-life balance. Iqbal et al., (2021), suggest that laissez-faire leadership style addresses strong attitudes, dependence, and trust in people inside an organization. This leadership style does not micromanage, provide explicit directions, or become engaged in any department. This leadership style empowers the millennials workforce to express their creativity in their work environments. Individuals can collaborate by sharing their expertise and resources to accomplish the organization's goals.

In a recent study conducted (Alifah & Sukmawati, 2021; Nor et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2024) on SMEs to understand the connection between leadership styles and job performance whereby adopting recommended strategies such as efficient data collection, multiple indicators consideration, control for confounding variables etc., SMEs can improve employee performance, foster loyalty, and achieve a competitive edge in the market. Leadership styles may contribute to the development of both leaders' leadership competencies as well as their subordinates' job performance and commitment (Sulantara et al., 2020; Mohamed et. al, 2022).

The empirical investigation on the moderating effect of employee acceptance towards the relationship between the three leadership styles and organizational change (H4, H5, H6) confirms that there is no moderating effects; and this may suggest that leadership style supersedes employee acceptance among millennial workforce in Klang Valley. This finding is uncommon since employee engagement has been a key mechanism through which leadership exerts its influence on organizational performance. Hence, this finding suggest that the effectiveness of a leadership style is heavily dependent on the situation and, critically, how employees respond to it.

CONCLUSION

This study adds substantial theoretical and practical value to the field of study. This research theoretically expands current knowledge about leadership styles together with their organizational change effects particularly among non-managerial employees located within Klang Valley vicinity. The research presents a research framework that evaluates how

participatory, laissez-faire and autocratic leadership styles influence organizational change success (Udin, 2023; Nor et al., 2024; Hamze & Sadiq, 2025). Non-managerial employees show a positive reaction to leadership styles that support autonomy because laissez-faire leadership proved to be most successful in generating beneficial change outcomes. These findings provide practical guidance to organizations in similar regions about implementing flexible leadership approaches with empowerment features (Knight, 2024) for their change implementation efforts. Leaders in organizations along with human resource departments must establish leadership development programs that explain the advantages of employee autonomy with self-directed decision authority. Leaders must have leadership skills that are needed to fit the present and the future workforce confronting the changing workforce and business landscape. This requires leaders to learn new soft skills and hard skills in order to sustain the organization e.g. visionary communicators, digital equipped, coach or motivators, and role models, adapting styles (like situational) to foster employee buy-in, reduce resistance, build trust, and create a positive culture for successful change, focusing on engagement, knowledge sharing, and tailored support for employees through uncertainty.

In the absence of employee engagement efforts, effective leadership is insufficient on its own. Programs for structured engagement should be put in place by managers. These programs should include participatory decision-making, frequent feedback mechanisms, and recognition systems. These programs promote commitment and loyalty by strengthening the psychological relationship between employees and the organization. Organizations may develop a motivated and resilient workforce that can adapt to changing company conditions by aligning engagement initiatives with leadership behaviours.

In light of these insights, organizations aiming for long-term sustainability and performance excellence need to support leadership development initiatives that integrate emotional intelligence, moral judgment, and employee empowerment. Additionally, this study paves way for further investigation into how these correlations appear in various organizational sizes, cultural contexts, and business sectors. In the millennial era, developing flexible, ethical, and inclusive leadership strategies that foster high levels of engagement and long-term organizational growth can be better understood by academics and professionals through the extension of this research. Initiatives for employee engagement should be combined with leadership strategies including frequent feedback channels, group decision-making, and reward programs to improve the psychological bonding between managers and employees. Organizations may develop a resilient, driven, and efficient workforce that can drive long-term success in the fast-paced marketplace of today by incorporating these concepts into leadership frameworks.

These findings are crucial for organizations to comprehend workers who started their careers in the new millennium since they tend to value independence at work. As a result, leadership styles must adapt to the preferences of different generations in order to promote employee engagement. Although this study produced insightful findings, it has several significant drawbacks. The survey's quantitative approach and structured questions restricted respondents' insight and provided little perspective into their own experiences. Additions to the research design, it should include qualitative methods that include interviews or focus groups to acquire deeper insights into the effects of leadership during a change implementation process.

The research would gain value by examining modern leadership approaches such as collaborative and inclusive leadership because this would help understand how modern workplace environment and new generational workforce expectations influence employee participation during change initiatives (Sharma et al., 2023).

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declared that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this study.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors contributed in the data collection, analysis, writing and revising the manuscript.

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